

ADVANTAGES OF SOCIAL NETWORKING SYSTEMS IN LEARNING ENGLISH

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Abstract: In today's modern world, technologies are becoming relevant in people's lives. These technologies also affect education, especially language learning. This article analyzes the role of social networking systems in language learning.

Keywords: Social network, Facebook, teaching, learning, process, skills, grammar, methods.

INTRODUCTION

Social network sites (SNS) such as My Space, hi5, Facebook, Twitter or Bebo have been gaining popularity since the first day of their invention, attracting the attention of academics and industry researchers. Teachers at all different educational levels (preschool, primary, elementary, middle, middle school and middle school and middle school and high school) and domains, design and implementation and acknowledged the support provided by the cooperative activities, receiving feedback. SNSs that promote personality, individuality, self-expression, self-affirmation, and communication serve the requirements and characteristics of a learner-centered approach to learning. This paper aims to provide a brief overview of how SNS can support English language teaching in terms of a student-centered approach to teaching and learning. The growing pedagogical interest in SNS has already given rise to a number of studies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A student-centered approach to the teaching-learning process focuses on the needs of students, not on the needs of teachers, on the involvement of students in

group work, on encouraging initiative and decision-making. The teacher's speech decreased dramatically, and the teacher's role shifted from the role of the main source of information to the role of mediator and guide. The specific goal of student-centered learning is to develop students into independent, autonomous learners by building and developing self-motivation and self-management skills, which will enable them to become independent learners in the future. can serve in self-education initiatives: "knowledge, instead of being objective and fixed, is to some extent personal, social and cultural. Meaning is constructed by the learner". The principles of student-centered education are as follows: - an active and voluntary learning process, during which meaning is discovered and constructed on the basis of information and experiences filtered by the student; The quantity and quality of information, feelings, motivations and perceptions in the construction of spiritual and knowledge, because the learning process is not unique: students' physical, emotional, intellectual, social development helps us learn, remember, understand and do how knowledge.

Active participation, social integration, self-reflection, and personal affirmation are at the core of the student-centered paradigm [13, 5]; A student-centered classroom environment should promote individualization, interaction, and integration [9, p. 21]. The growing pedagogical interest in SNSs may be primarily due to their popularity: given that most students have one or more accounts on SNSs, popularity translates into time savings. , how to use such sites; the user-friendly interface of such sites can reduce the effort of the teacher in introducing such a possible educational tool to the students; From the point of view of our paper, the quality that we consider the most important is the sharing of information only to users at the same time (a class of students) and simultaneously and in real time. Another feature of SNSs is related to the exchange of information in various formats: texts, videos, images, links.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Communication and interaction on SNSs is a continuation of real-life communication and interaction, understood as mutual action and influence. Students use SNS for reasons such as: existing relationships for existing relationships; meet new people; for entertainment; make themselves famous; passage of time; self-expression; study; managing tasks and homework. On SNSs, students can receive pieces of information and reproduce, share, or send them to their friend groups, thereby engaging in mentoring and advising activities. According to the student-centered approach, students should be given learning skills so that they can develop their own learning styles and become lifelong learners.

There are some recommendations that a teacher should consider before deciding to use an SNS as an educational tool: the age of the students and the age-related policies of the SNS; Teachers and students should not share their personal information through SNSs; the teacher's tone should remain professional in online communication; Professionalism should also be the key word associated with photos, materials, videos and all comments and comments and all comments and messages posted and read to students through SNS; in turn, students must demonstrate professional and respectful behavior; Displaying online information about online learning should avoid students who are uncomfortable with it or avoid the instructor's preferences for any student or other student; While students in the classroom can have their own online group, teachers can also join various professional online groups related to their field of work. We present our ideas and recommendations for teaching English as a foreign language, which can be adapted and adapted to different ages and skill levels, as well as other subjects.

CONCLUSION

The teacher can invite students to participate in activities similar to those held in the classroom, for example: commenting on a quotation, commenting on a literary passage, giving their own explanations for newly introduced words, concepts and concepts. Such activities conducted online via SNS are a continuation of classroom

tasks, as well as an opportunity for students to provide feedback that they may not have during the actual class as time is usually limited to 50 minutes.

In addition, such activities can bring out the best in (shy) students and improve self-expression and self-expression. They can use SNS or study resources or distribute them to the whole group/class of students. Online links can direct students to materials necessary for learning English as a foreign language, such as: online dictionaries and encyclopedias, official pages of studied authors, museum websites, works by various authors, available online critical approaches. the authors studied. Such links encourage students to search for their own knowledge, choose information, find new facts, and ultimately contribute to the creation of a unique, unique, learning style. Students can be created by the teacher or other students, for example, online projects, such as the English menu of the relevant social network, and Facebook / Twitter using the English language in English All communication through the relevant SNS: each student using the name of their favorite character is relevant Logs into an SNS account and completes profile information, posts status updates, comments, pictures, or photos that the student deems appropriate. appropriate sign. Such a project can be completed by voting for the best character SNS account.

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